

PROBLEMS OF ENSURING INFORMATION SECURITY IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE OFFICER PERSONNEL AND THEIR SOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the modern methods of training military teaching personnel, the potential for developing their innovative abilities, the importance of the innovative approach in this direction, the possibilities of achieving effective results in the training process, as well as the levels and scope of the acmeological approach in pedagogical skills are covered.

Keywords: military, innovative, qualified pedagogical, acmeological, information security, personnel.

INTRODUCTION

The need to systematically improve the qualifications of military pedagogues is the development of modern weapons and technology in the Armed Forces, the implementation of the military education system using modern methods, the role of military pedagogues in the training of competitive officer personnel, the ability to analyze the work experience of advanced pedagogues and use them in practice, exchange ideas, and It is determined by the ability to provide assistance, pedagogical skills, and the ability to make the right decisions in pedagogical situations.

In modern conditions, there are various approaches to the process of upgrading the skills of military teachers. One of them is the acmeological approach.

The acmeological approach was promoted by educational scientists A.A. Derkach, S.N. Tolstov, N.B. Kovaleva, A.S. Oding, I.O. Sorokina, N.M. Egamberdieva, and the innovative ability of military teaching staff as a scientific basis of development, it is based on the visibility of the teachers of the military higher education country as participants of this process, mature persons and active subjects of professional activity, and it creates conditions for their continuous self-improvement and self-development step by step as subjects and specialists.

From the acmeological point of view, innovative competence serves as a basic concept for describing the speed, effectiveness, originality of the process of the emergence of innovations, the ability to create, perceive, and implement new innovations, as well as the psychological mechanism that ensures the implementation

of this process - reflection. N.G. Alekseev and I.N.Semenov proposed the analysis of practical activity [2, 3-4].

Innovation competence has the following features:

1. Directed to introduce various news;
2. Based on the introduction of temporary changes related to the specific situation.

If the main description of the first view is the ability of military pedagogues-personnel to engage in creative professional activity and self-development, the main aspect of the second view is the peculiarities and conditions of the military pedagogic profession, that is, the positive attitude of the participants to the results of innovative changes, the acceptance of the new environment seems to depend on groups' consent.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Acmeological abilities - self-understanding, self-development, self-disclosure, etc., are of great importance in the process of human life but their rapid development occurs as a result of the development of autopsychological competence.

Institutional Governance Institutional governance is critical to the success of any given level of governance. These are business-oriented processes that have a perspective and focus on issues that affect the organization (eg: business administration, academic affairs, student services, etc.). Online learning courses require careful curriculum planning, including the following elements: Learning environment. An online learning environment is a place where students access online resources, use online course and communication systems, receive teacher support, and receive assessments. People learn best in learning environments that are supportive, comforting, and casual. Thus, the learning environment should be comfortable in all aspects, such as physicality, trust, respect, support and freedom. At the same time, the online learning environment does not have a great impact on the learning outcomes, but it has the ability to create an appropriate learning environment in the online learning course. facilitate the delivery, monitoring and testing of online training courses. Provides a set of tools and templates that allow the instructor to relatively easily create online course content and then teach and manage that course, including providing a variety of interactions with learners in the course. contains z. Technical Infrastructure - Technology plays an important role in delivering learning outcomes as students interact more in online learning environments to be successful. The University must have quality supporting technology with up-to-date and appropriate transfer data for online courses.

Access and navigation (interface design) is the technical support to facilitate the communication and learning activities of the online course. Students can easily log in to enhance their learning experience in an online environment, such as instant access to a website. Course access requirements are compliance with system policies

Self-psychological abilities of a person include the following: 1) general - self-relationship, ability to control oneself; 2) related to knowledge - developmental psychology and intelligence as a higher level of consciousness unique to humans; 3) in the acmeological content of cognitive-creative activity, cognition is reflected in the interaction of self-awareness and professional activity; 4) creative - finding non-standard ways of solving creative tasks, imagining and creating new symbols; social-perceptive - social-perceptive is reflected in the interpersonal interaction of self-evaluation in acmeological content; about empathy - susceptibility to emotional influence; adaptability to emotional influences [3, 12].

Based on the research of A.A. Derkach, S.P. Tolstov and N.M. Egumberdieva, we have developed a model for the development of innovative competence of military teaching personnel based on an acmeological approach. Below we will focus on the components of this model separately.

The model includes four interrelated components: 1) motivational and qualitative; 2) cognitive; 3) active; 4) creative.

The motivational and personnel component of the model consists of motivational and personnel components. The motivational component reflects aspects of the melody:

- 1) the existence of a sustainable internal need for knowledge and professional motivation;
- 2) striving for productive activity;
- 3) willingness to actively participate in innovative processes;
- 4) the need to make one's face visible.

An important factor in the development of innovative skills in professional pedagogues is professional interest. Professional interest expresses interest in the contents of a clearly defined field of activity. In this process, curiosity to know encourages the acquisition of existing forms and methods of activity. It is worth noting that interest in this or that creative activity is related to the development of talent for it.

A qualitative component of the development of innovative competence includes a positive creative attitude to work. A permanent and non-personal interest in pedagogical innovations should be present in the creation of a competent component.

The cognitive component of the model is based on the level and quality of regular familiarization with new professional knowledge and information related to the profession. The development of the cognitive component provides a system for the development of professional competence within the framework of the development of the innovative competence of the military pedagogue-staff. Apart from this, the cognitive component includes attentive, responsible attitude to responsible work, constant readiness. The cognitive component is also related to intellectual activity, i.e.,

the uniqueness of thinking, the speed of the thinking process, the systematicity of mental movements, increasing the ability to analyze and generalize, and the high productivity of mental activity. The cognitive component is largely related to the formation of the professional culture of the military pedagogue-personnel.

The readiness of the professional pedagogue to implement innovations in pedagogical activity depends on the acquisition of innovative skills and qualifications. The active structural part includes cognitive, planning, communicative and organizational elements of solving creative tasks. In many respects, the level of professional creativity of the military pedagogue, the extent to which the main signs of creativity are reflected in the new and re-organization of the main signs of creativity, determine the effective manifestation of the active structural part. Identifying the current opportunities and prospects of creative development in the future in terms of design; compliance with pedagogic activities in solving creative tasks, choosing creative methods of activity, intelligent planning of activities, directions and mechanisms for achieving expected results are determined. The communicative aspect includes the restoration of personal and professional relationships in the team and the successful exchange of pedagogical innovations among colleagues in solving creative tasks. Such parts of creative activity as self-organization and self-control are part of the element of organization.

As the central part of the model of development of the innovative competence of professional pedagogues-staff, the acmeological approach reflects the creative component that reflects the ability for effective creative activity. Exactly development of creativity is one of the main goals of developing the innovative competence of military pedagogues based on the acmeological approach. The ability to think innovatively in modern rapidly changing conditions is one of the important professional qualities of a professional pedagogue. The creative component is the ability to creative thinking, creative learning, educational, research activities; a desire to create something new, to solve pedagogical tasks intelligently, to be able to independently plan one's work; It includes the formation of mental situations that allow solving professional creative tasks.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above ideas, it should be emphasized that the development of innovative competence in the process of upgrading the skills of military teaching staff requires an approach in the form of modeling of this process, based on specific theoretical and methodological foundations. The effective use of the systematic, axiological and acmeological models of the development of the innovative competence of military teachers-personnel revealed in the research during the training process lays the groundwork for achieving the expected results.

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